

Papić-Blagojević, N., Tomašević, S., Račić, Ž, & Savić, M. (2022). Challenges and examples of apparent good practice developed in the PRO-VET project in VET teacher education in the Republic of Serbia. In C. Nägele, N. Kersh, & B. E. Stalder (Eds.), *Trends in vocational education and training research, Vol. V. Proceedings of the European Conference on Educational Research (ECER), Vocational Education and Training Network (VETNET)* (pp. 150–161). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6977540>

Challenges and Examples of Apparent Good Practice Developed in the PRO-VET Project in VET Teacher Education in the Republic of Serbia

Papić-Blagojević, Nataša

npavic.blagojevic@gmail.com, Novi Sad School of Business, Serbia

Tomašević, Stevan

tomasevic.vps@gmail.com, Novi Sad School of Business, Serbia

Račić, Željko

raciczeljko@gmail.com, Novi Sad School of Business, Serbia

Savić, Mirko

savimirko@ef.uns.ac.rs, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Economics, Serbia

Abstract

Context: This study is part of an Erasmus+ KA2 CBHE project, „Professional Development of Vocational Education Teachers with European Practices/Pro-VET“, and it represents one of the final results of the conducted research and delivered courses among VET teachers in the Republic of Serbia.

Approach: The research is based on three iterations of VOOC titled „Effective team working for VET teachers according to EU practice“ developed during the project life and the evaluation results of that process. All participants, 192 in total, have had an opportunity to fill out the questionnaire about using group and team working in their everyday teaching activities and express their knowledge about these topics before the iteration starts. The results are summarised and presented through descriptive statistics, and logistic regression was used to measure the level of significance of the selected variables.

Findings: Empirical research was conducted by collecting and analysing primary data using a survey method. To meet the needs of VET teachers in the Republic of Serbia, an online survey was designed, which referred to teachers' attitudes on team working in VET institutions. The research results are based on the sample, which included 192 respondents. Statistical analyses of all collected data (descriptive statistics, linear correlation, logistic regression analysis) were used to draw conclusions about the relationships between the observed variables.

Conclusion: Logistic regression analysis confirmed that the strongest and statistically significant predictor of the answer that teachers use teamwork is synergy. Other factors do not have a statistically significant effect on the use of teamwork. This research has shown several conclusions: communication in teams is open but not practical; despite adequate leadership, the roles in the teams are not clearly defined; and as a result, the team members do not have a strong sense of belonging to the team. It reduces the synergistic effect.

Keywords: professional development, vet teachers, online training, team working skills

1 Introduction

The professional development of teachers in the Republic of Serbia is regulated by appropriate national acts and defined legal frameworks which prescribe the need and necessity of continuous training as a legal obligation. The importance of the professional development of educational professionals is universal (Seunke et al., 2021). In Serbia, the reform of the professional development of teachers began in 2002. After that, the legal obligation of continuous professional development of employees in education was introduced by the national authorities (Papić-Blagojević et al., 2020). The teacher training process was further developed and improved through policy definition and creating a system of professional development of teachers at the national level.

Teacher competencies are defined within the Rulebook on Competence Standards for the teaching profession and their professional development (2011), which explains the socially expected roles of teachers that are the basis for defining the training content. The Rulebook on the Continuing Professional Development of Teachers (2021) defines professional development as a complex process aimed at the constant review and development of employees' competencies in the education system. Concurrently, a vital goal of the Strategy for the Development of Education in the Republic of Serbia until 2030 (2021) is the professional development of employees in education to raise the capacity and quality of teaching staff. The Action Plan from 2021 to 2023 for the Strategy's implementation (2021) defines the priorities for systematically implementing specific measures and activities to improve education development. One of the main goals is the professional development of teachers at all levels, and one of the particular actions is related to improving teacher competencies in vocational studies (Burns et al., 2020). In this way, Serbia has announced and launched various reforms to address a growing demand for a better and more equitable education system (Maghnouj et al., 2020).

In Serbia, the importance of continuing professional development (CPD) for VET teachers is not in question (Maksimović, 2016). Still, research conducted in 2016 has shown that most respondents (75 %) think it is primarily their responsibility to identify their own CPD needs. Regarding the respondents' current needs, 65 % claim a moderate or high level of demand for implementing new technologies in the workplace, for ICT skills, 56 %, and for teaching cross-curricular skills 53 % (Maksimović, 2016). Some findings of the research conducted in 2016 by the European Training Foundation underline the need for further improvement, especially in the VET teachers' education field in Serbia, considering it as a separate component of the CPD system (Burns et al., 2020).

Rulebook on the Continuing Professional Development of Teachers, Pre-School Teachers and Professional Associates (2016) was introduced in 2016 to overcome the lack of needed skills, recognising and regulating online training delivery. To encourage teachers to use online platforms and digital tools in teaching, the national Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development published the Digital Competence Framework – Digital Age Teacher in 2017 to support teachers from the education system in Serbia in integrating digital content into everyday practice. The document lists and defines the skills, goals and expected outcomes that form a corpus of digital competencies of the teaching profession. Since then, online training has become an increasingly popular form of professional development and is also frequently organised by education authorities (Progress report, 2018).

Guided by national priorities on the professional development of VET teachers, Pro-VET project team members from the University of Novi Sad and the Novi Sad School of Business have developed an online training course to develop team-working skills of VET teachers. The course is designed under the supervision of EU project partners, JAMK University of Applied Sciences, Finland, Universität Bremen, Institut Technik und Bildung, Warnborough College, Ireland, and Aeres University of Applied Sciences Wageningen, Netherlands.

Creating a high-quality online course should have grounds in researching teachers' needs, and it should cover some of the specific demands of VET teachers' development (Burns et al., 2020). The need for developing team-working teachers' skills arises from two research conducted in 2019 as a part of the Pro-VET project. In the first research, the Serbian project team surveyed 125 teachers of different professions (Papić-Blagojević et al., 2020). It included an assessment of the level of teacher competencies, soft skills and the need for additional pedagogical and psychological, as well as methodological education necessary for the successful implementation of teaching.

The research results showed that, out of the total number of respondents, as many as 31.5 % of VET teachers in their previous formal or non-formal education had not had the opportunity to acquire knowledge and develop competencies in this area. Also, 31.4 % of respondents received knowledge on their initiative by studying professional literature without attending formal training programmes. The results also indicate that a tiny percentage (2.4 %) of teachers participated in some form of online training and professional development program, which implies that most teachers if they opt for some training, focus on programmes that take place in actual circumstances (Lungulov et al., 2021). The research has also shown an interest in further training and professional development. Some of the proposed training topics focus on acquiring pedagogical and psychological knowledge, for example, new learning methods, cooperative learning, group work in teaching, etc. Also, the respondents have shown interest in getting additional computer knowledge such as applying new technologies in education, using educational platforms, etc. There was also an interest in developing soft skills like teamwork, conflict resolution, student motivation, etc.

The second research was conducted to develop the course content that would best meet the needs of teachers in VET schools in Serbia (Papić-Blagojević et al., 2021). The „Attitudes of VET teachers on group and team working in educational institutions“ questionnaire was delivered to 138 teachers in different VET institutions. The results have shown that even 39.9 % of teachers answered that they were not motivated to use group work in class. Also, 67.4 % of surveyed teachers do not use the learner-centred approach. At the same time, in part about team-working skills, 46.4 % of respondents state that there is no effective communication among the team members in the teams where they belong, and 48.6 % do not feel like important team members. These results encouraged Pro-VET project members from Serbia to develop an online course, „Effective team working for VET teachers according to EU practice“.

2 Team Working and its Role in the Professional Development of Teachers

Teamwork can be analysed, observed and used from different aspects and for different meanings. Teamwork is a generic and transversal skill characterised by its relational dimension. It is defined as the capacity to integrate into and interact with work groups, striving toward achieving common goals (Romero-Díaz de la Guardia et al., 2022; Anderson-Butcher et al., 2014; Barraycoa-Martínez & Lasaga-Millet, 2010; González & Wagenaar, 2003). When we talk about teamwork and its more frequent use in teaching, it is one way to ensure interdisciplinary education, overcome the isolation of certain teaching subjects, and ensure rational use of teaching staff and school space (Papić-Blagojević et al., 2021; Španović & Đukić, 2006). Teamwork is usually represented in teachers' organisational, advisory, and administrative work, primarily within projects, while in teaching activities, it occurs rarely and sporadically (Vasiljević et al., 2017).

The literature usually defines teachers' teamwork as the joint and cooperative work of two or more teachers of the same or different professions based on cooperation, exchanging ideas and opinions. Teamwork, defined like this, aims to achieve the goals defined by the teaching process, improve the quality of teaching and learning and, finally, contribute to teachers' professional development. Erb and Dickinson (1997) consider that the team is most often expressed

through the work of two or more teachers with shared responsibility for teaching the same group of students. Forming a team of teachers is a process. In order to create a good, cooperative team, it is necessary to slowly and carefully develop a climate of trust among team members to recognise, engage and evaluate the abilities and skills of each teacher (Đukić & Španović, 2008). Teamwork in education should be supported by understanding its theoretical foundations and appropriate skills and training for its planning and implementation (Main, 2010).

3 Empirical Research About the Use of Teamwork in Teaching Practice

3.1 General Notes and Frequency Analysis

Empirical research started with expanding the primary research conducted in 2019 to develop the course content that would best meet the needs of teachers in VET schools in Serbia. Based on a literature review about teamwork, selected findings were adapted and included in the questionnaire „Attitudes of VET teachers on group and team working in educational institutions “. Empirical research was conducted using a survey method. To meet the needs of teachers in VET institutions in the Republic of Serbia, the authors conducted an online survey, which referred to teachers' attitudes on team working in VET institutions. The research results are based on the sample, which included 192 respondents.

The survey was structured in several parts. The first part of the research provides general data from the sample (gender, age, work experience). The second part of the survey, „Use of teamwork in teaching”, aimed to assess whether and how VET teachers in Serbia use teamwork in everyday teaching. The third part of the survey includes 25 statements and seeks to estimate the level of teamwork efficiency across the VET institutions in the Republic of Serbia. This part analysed three crucial aspects of teamwork efficiency: synergy in teams, encouraging innovation and development of team skills. The degree of agreement with the statements was measured using the Likert five-point scale, where one (1) indicates that the respondent absolutely disagrees and five (5) completely agrees with the statement.

SPSS (The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) is used to analyse the collected data. Statistical methods of analysing data in this study were implemented as follows: descriptive statistical analysis, correlation, and logistic regression analysis. The first step applied descriptive statistical analysis to the whole sample. Arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for each variable to determine the homogeneity/heterogeneity of teachers' attitudes. The reliability of the obtained variables and the internal consistency of the accompanying findings were measured based on values of the alpha coefficient (Cronbach's alpha). Before performing the regression analysis, correlation analysis is presented, i.e. the degree of linearity was checked dependencies (correlations) between variables. Finally, logistic regression analysis determined the statistical significance of the influences identified by variables on the use of teamwork.

Table 1 is shown that of 192 respondents, 77.6 % are female, while 22.4 % are male. Most respondents (79.2 %) are between the ages of 30 and 55, while only 4.7 % are under 30. Finally, 62.5 % of respondents have between 11 and 30 years of work experience, while those with more than 31 years of teaching experience are 14.6 %. Based on the previous information, it was concluded that the sample consists mainly of younger and middle-aged female persons with work experience of over ten years.

Over 81 % of respondents answered that they use teamwork primarily within professional bodies at the institution, and 88 % do it often within the teaching classes. It is essential to emphasise that among VET teachers, there is a lack of motivation regarding using groups or teamwork. According to survey results, more than 36 % of respondents are not motivated to be part of the teams. Thus, it can be said that creating and implementing an online course about teamwork

can be very useful for raising the competencies of VET teachers in Serbia and bringing the quality of the teaching process closer to European best practices.

Table 1

General data - Frequency

	Frequency	%
Gender		
Female	149	77,6
Male	43	22,4
Age		
Less than 30 years	9	4.7
Between 30 and 55 years	152	79.2
More than 55 years	31	16.1
Work experience		
Less than 10 years	44	22.9
Between 11 and 30 years	120	62.5
More than 30 years	28	14.6
Use teamwork within professional bodies at the institution		
Yes	156	81.3
No	36	18.7
Use teamwork within the teaching classes		
Yes	169	88
No	23	12

Note. Author's calculation.

Over 81 % of respondents answered that they use teamwork primarily within professional bodies at the institution, and 88 % do it often within the teaching classes. It is essential to emphasise that among VET teachers, there is a lack of motivation regarding using groups or teamwork. According to survey results, more than 36 % of respondents are not motivated to be part of the teams. Thus, it can be said that creating and implementing an online course about teamwork can be very useful for raising the competencies of VET teachers in Serbia and bringing the quality of the teaching process closer to European best practices.

Sinergy as the combined power of a group and more significant than the total power achieved by each working separately presents one of the essential effects of teamwork. Consequently, the authors wanted to investigate respondents' attitudes related to issues, significantly determining the power of the synergistic impact within teamwork. The obtained answers are presented in Figure 1.

Using a Likert scale from 1 (completely disagree) to 5 (completely agree), respondents expressed a degree of personal agreement on the following questions: (1) Belonging to each team is clearly defined; (2) The goal of the team I belong to is clearly defined; (3) Every member of the team is clear about their role in the team; (4) Team communication is efficient; (5) I feel like an important member of the team; (6) I am proud to belong to my team; (7) Each team member strives to the maximum during the team's work and (8) Team leadership is efficient and adequate.

Based on the obtained answers, it can be concluded that the aims of teamwork and leadership are clearly defined. On the other hand, the respondents assessed that they do not have a strong sense of belonging to the teams. In addition, they showed a lower degree of agreement with the claims that roles in teams are assigned precisely, and that communication in teams is effective.

Figure 1
Estimation of synergy effect in teamwork

The second important aspect of teamwork efficiency is innovation, i.e. encouraging team members to use innovative approaches in teamwork and problem-solving. Innovations commonly involve changes to an array of processes and are rarely the result of one individual's activity. Thus, teamwork and cooperation are essential to implement innovation effectively. To assess the use of teamwork to encourage innovation, respondents provided answers to the following questions: (1) Team members are encouraged to try new teaching methods; (2) Every innovation in the work of the team is appreciated and rewarded; (3) Problems in the work of the team are quickly detected; (4) Issues in the work of the team are solved rapidly, and (5) Problem-solving is perceived as team learning and team development. The obtained results are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2
Estimation of innovation support

The primary impression gained from the responses is that innovation within teamwork is not appreciated and rewarded enough. Therefore, team members are not encouraged to apply innovative learning methods. Weaker encouragement of an innovative approach to teamwork

reduces the dynamic of spotting and solving problems, despite respondents understanding that an innovative approach to problem-solving is an excellent opportunity for team learning and development.

Improving teamwork to harmonise the work of VET teachers with the best EU practice is conditioned by acquiring new knowledge and skills. Therefore, the authors estimated the respondents' attitudes regarding employers' support in providing additional training related to the development of teamwork. Also, in this part of the research, the goal was to assess whether there is a need to organise such training. Using the same measurement scale, respondents expressed their degree of agreement with some of the following statements: (1) All team members are well trained and competent for their job; (2) Employees are provided with additional training following the analysed needs; (3) The team members' team role is clearly defined; (4) There is an effective mechanism for resolving conflicts within the team and (5) Communication in the team is open. The obtained results are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3

Estimation skills development support

Based on the obtained answers, it can be concluded that more than 40 % of respondents believe that there is a need for additional training to raise the competencies of VET teachers in the field of teamwork. The assessment supports that more than half of the respondents have not participated in the training of this type so far. Finally, the results assess that there is the greatest need for organising training in the field of responsibilities diversification within teams (assigning team roles), as well as in resolving conflicts within teams.

There are several significant conclusions of the research. First, communication in teams is open but not practical. Second, despite adequate leadership, the roles in the teams are not clearly defined, and as a result, the team members do not have a strong sense of belonging to the team. It reduces the synergistic effect. In addition, innovation in teams is not sufficiently supported, slowing down the process of adjusting VET practice in Serbia to European best practices. Based on all the above, the conclusion is that the organisation of additional training in acquiring the skills of teamwork of VET teachers is necessary, with which the participants in the research agree.

3.2 Research Results and Discussion

Using descriptive statistical analysis, the arithmetic means and standard deviation values were calculated based on 25 selected statements that were grouped into three independent variables

(synergy, innovation, and skills). The results of the descriptive statistical analysis indicate that the most favourable attitude of the teacher is expressed in the first two statements. These statements indicate that the affiliation to a particular team is clearly defined and that the meaning/goal of the team to which the teacher belongs is clearly defined (the mean value is 4.10). The lowest average grade was obtained for the statement that every innovation in the team's work is appreciated and rewarded (the mean value is 3.15). The given statement also shows the most considerable heterogeneity of responses among respondents, which means that with this claim, there is the highest degree of disagreement among respondents because the value of the standard deviation is 1.25. The lowest standard deviation value (1.022) was obtained when stating that the affiliation to a particular team is clearly defined. This statement has the highest degree of agreement among respondents.

The reliability and consistency of the findings were measured via Cronbach's alpha coefficient. The values of this coefficient are shown in Table 2.

Table 2
Cronbach's alpha coefficients

Variables	Values of Cronbach's alpha coefficients
Synergy	0.937
Innovation	0.932
Skills	0.956

Note. Authors' calculation by SPSS.

Cronbach's alpha coefficient values range from 0 to 1, with coefficient values preferably greater than 0.7, indicating adequate reliability and consistency of claims (Nunnally, 1978). Robinson et al. (1991) consider values greater than 0.6 acceptable. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient values for all three independent variables are over 0.9 and indicate adequate reliability and internal consistency. Cronbach's alpha for the whole model is 0.975.

Before performing the regression analysis, it is necessary to perform a correlation test (correlation analysis), i.e. to check the degree of dependence between the three independent model variables. There are numerous linear correlation measures, but the most frequently used measure, i.e. the Pearson coefficient, will be used in this paper.

Table 3
Correlation analysis/Pearson correlation

	SYNERGY	INNOVATION	SKILLS
SYNERGY	1		
INNOVATION	.772**	1	
SKILLS	.817**	.869**	1

Note. N = 192, ** correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The intercorrelation matrix testifies to the significant values of the Pearson coefficient. There is a statistically significant correlation between all variables included in the model (Table 3). The results of the correlation analysis show a high degree of correlation between all independent variables (0.772-0.869).

Logistic regression analysis is used to determine which variables significantly impact the use of teamwork in teaching. Through this analysis, the influence of independent variables (synergy, innovation, skills) on the use of teamwork as dependent variables was tested. In this

regard, the category variable will be used as a dependent variable, i.e. the statement „Do you use teamwork in working with students?“.

Before interpreting the regression model results, it is necessary to examine whether all the assumptions about the adequacy of the model are met. In other words, it is required to explore the model's performance and determine how well it predicts the results. The test that confirms this assumption is the Hasmer and Lemeshow test. Based on the results, the Hasmer and Lemeshow test ($\chi^2 = 9.955$; $p = 0.268$) shows that the result is not statistically significant, and the model is satisfactory, so the basic assumption is met, and further analysis can be continued.

The following assumption is to examine the model's utility through the value of the coefficient of determination (pseudo r^2), which shows which part of the variance of the dependent variable (the use of teamwork) explains the model. However, the stated value of the pseudo coefficient of determination should be interpreted with caution. Most authors believe there are no clear guidelines on how this coefficient should be used and interpreted (Pituch & Stevens, 2016). As most researchers recommend the Nagelkerke coefficient of determination, the authors concluded that the set of independent predictors explains 11.8 % of the variance of the dependent variable.

When analysing the final model, it is concluded that the statistical significance of only one of the three defined independent variables was determined. The variable synergy has proven to be a statistically significant explanatory variable. The obtained result shows that it is likely that there will be an increase in the use of teamwork if some of the elements of synergies are raised to a higher level (Table 4).

Table 4
Variables in the Equation

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95 % C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
SYNERGY	1.244	.491	6.430	1	.011	3.470	1.326	9.080
INNOVATION	.370	.490	.571	1	.450	1.448	.554	3.787
SKILLS	-1.011	.580	3.039	1	.081	.364	.117	1.134
Constant	-.269	.866	.096	1	.756	.764		

Note. Author's calculation by SPSS.

As shown in Table 4, only one independent variable makes a statistically significant contribution to the model (synergy). The strongest predictor of the answer that teachers use teamwork was synergy, whose probability quotient is 3,470. It shows that respondents who support synergies in a team more often answer that they are ready to use teamwork than those who are not prepared to use the same. The remaining two independent variables, innovation and skills, are not statistically significant predictors.

4 Conclusion

The research that was conducted as a part of an Erasmus+ KA2 CBHE project, „Professional Development of Vocational Education Teachers with European Practices/Pro-VET“, has shown the need for further professional development of VET teachers in the Republic of Serbia. The research has also demonstrated that teamwork in everyday teaching activities is necessary for creating an efficient working environment that will provide achieving the goals defined by the teaching process and improve the quality of teaching and learning.

Particularly, logistic regression analysis confirmed that the strongest and statistically significant predictor of the answer that teachers use teamwork is synergy. Other factors do not have a statistically significant effect on the use of teamwork. The obtained result showed that it is likely that there will be an increase in the use of teamwork if some of the elements of synergies are raised to a higher level.

This research also points out several conclusions: communication in teams is open but not practical; despite adequate leadership, the roles in the teams are not clearly defined; and as a result, the team members do not have a strong sense of belonging to the team; it reduces the synergistic effect. In addition, innovation in teams is not sufficiently supported, slowing down the process of adjusting VET practice in Serbia to European best practices. Based on all the above, the conclusion is that the organisation of additional training in acquiring the skills of teamwork of VET teachers is necessary, with which the participants in the research have agreed.

Based on the needs analysis and the research conclusions, an online course, „Effective team working for VET teachers following EU practice”, was designed. The course is designed for teachers who want to develop skills and competencies in teamwork. It offers theoretical and practical knowledge about teams and raises awareness of the importance of teamwork for 21st-century teachers. The first part of the course includes introducing students to the benefits of teamwork, the differences between teams and groups, the essential elements of the team, the stages in team development, and roles and responsibilities in the team. The second part of the course emphasises the importance and role of communication in decision-making and resolving conflict situations in teamwork. The course also analyses the various decision-making pitfalls that teams may fall into and how to develop better decision-making practices. The third part is dedicated to introducing modern digital technologies to improve teachers' teamwork skills and performance.

Three iterations of the developed course were successfully implemented. As a result of participants' positive reactions to the three-course iterations, an official request was submitted to the Institute for the Advancement of Education (the regulatory body approving teacher professional development programmes) to accredit the course „Development and application of teamwork in everyday teaching practice”. Meanwhile, the authors have received a formal confirmation for the course accreditation. The course will be a part of the catalogue of approved programmes for Continuous professional development of teachers, educators and professional associates for the academic year 2022/2023, 2023/2024 and 2024/2025.

Acknowledgement

This paper is written as a result of the Erasmus+ KA2 project Capacity Building in Higher Education „Professional Development of Vocational Education Teachers with European Practices Pro-VET”, EACEA 598698-EPP-1-2018-1-FI-EPPKA2-CBHE-JP, funded and supported by the Erasmus+ programme of the European Union and co-financed by the Provincial Secretariat for Finance of the Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia.

References

- Anderson-Butcher, D., Amorose, T., Lower, L., Riley, A., Gibson, A., & Ruch, D. (2014). The case for the perceived social competence scale-II. *Research on social work practice*, 26(4), 419–428. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049731514557362>
- Barraycoa-Martínez, J., & Lasaga-Millet, O. (2010). The teamwork competency: Beyond the cut and paste. *Vivat Academia*, 111, 65–69. <https://doi.org/10.15178/va.2010.111.65-69>
- Burns, E., Silvennoinen, E., Kopnov, V. A., Shchipanova, D. E., Papić-Blagojević, N., & Tomašević, S. (2020). Supporting the development of digitally competent VET teachers in Serbia and Russia. *The Education and Science Journal*, 22(9), 174–203. <https://doi.org/10.17853/1994-5639-2020-9-174-203>
- Đukić, M., & Španović, M. (2008). Efektivno partnerstvo nastavnika kao činilac kvaliteta timske nastave. *Nastava i vaspitanje*, 57(3), 259-272.
- Erb, T. O., & Dickinson, T. S. (1997). The future of teaming. In T. S. Dickinson & T. O. Erb (Eds.), *We gain more than we give. Teaming in middle schools* (pp. 525-540). Columbus: National Middle Association.
- González, J., & Wagenaar, R. (2003). *Tuning educational structures in Europe. Informe final, fase I*. University of Deusto. http://tuningacademy.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/02/TuningEUI_Final-Report_SP.pdf

- Lungulov, B., Papić-Blagojević, N., & Savić, M. (2021). On-line courses in higher education as an opportunity for lifelong teacher education. In V. Katić (Ed.), *XXVII Skup Trendovi razvoja: On-line nastava na univerzitetima* (pp. 265-268). Novi Sad: Faculty of Science.
- Maghnouj, S., Salinas, D., Kitchen, H., Guthrie, C., Bethell, G., & Fordham, E. (2020). *OECD Reviews of Evaluation and Assessment in Education: Serbia*. <https://doi.org/10.1787/225350d9-en>
- Main, K. (2010). Teamwork – Teach me, teach me not: A case study of three Australian preservice teachers. *The Australian Educational Researcher*, 37(3), 77-93.
- Maksimović, I. (2016). *Continuing professional development for vocational teachers and trainers in Serbia*. European Training Foundation. https://www.etf.europa.eu/sites/default/files/m/A87A22FCE871D3C2C1257FCD005F8D23_CPD%20Serbia.pdf
- Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia. (2021). *Action plan from 2021 to 2023 for the implementation of the strategy for the development of education until 2030*. <https://www.mpn.gov.rs/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/AP-Strategija.docx.pdf>
- Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia. (2017). *Digital competence framework – Digital age teacher*. <https://www.mpn.gov.rs/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/Okvir-digitalnih-kompetencija-Final-2.pdf>
- Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia. (2018). *Progress report on the action plan for the implementation of the strategy for education development in Serbia by 2020*. <http://www.mpn.gov.rs/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/AP-SROS-IZVESTAJ-15jun-Eng.pdf>
- Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia. (2021). *Strategy of education development in the republic of Serbia until 2030*. https://www.mpn.gov.rs/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/1-SROVRS-2030_MASTER_0402_V1.pdf
- Nunnally, J. C. (1978). *Introduction to psychological measurement*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia. (2021). *Rulebook on the continuing professional development of teachers, pre-school teachers and professional associates*. Official gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 109/2021. <https://www.paragraf.rs/propisi/pravilnik-strucnom-usavrsavanju-napredovanju-zvanja-nastavnika-vaspitaca-strucnih.html>
- Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia. (2016). *Rulebook on the continuing professional development of teachers, pre-school teachers and professional associates*. Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 109/2021.86/2015, 3/2016, 73/2016. <https://www.zuov.gov.rs/starisajt/ostali-propisi/index.html>
- Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia. (2011). *Rulebook on standards of competences for the teaching profession and their professional development*. Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 5/2011. Available on: <https://zuov.gov.rs/download/pravilnik-o-standardima-kompetencija-za-profesiju-nastavnika-i-njihovog-profesionalnog-razvoja/>
- Papić-Blagojević, N., Lungulov, B., & Milišić, N. (2020). Professional development of vocational teachers-developmental possibilities through projects of capacity building. In V. Katić (Ed.), *XXVI Skup Trendovi razvoja: Inovacije u modernom obrazovanju* (pp. 450-453). Novi Sad: Faculty of Science.
- Papić-Blagojević, N., Račić, Ž., & Tomašević, S. (2021). Team working skills as an important part of the professional development of vet teachers. In R.K. Gilmeeva & L.A. Shibankova (Ed.), *Pedagogical readings 2021: Humanitarian vector of education in the era of digitalisation* (pp. 237-242). Kazan: Federal State Budget Scientific Institution Institute of Pedagogy, Psychology and Social Problems.
- Pituch, K.A., Stevens, J.A. (2016). *Applied multivariate statistics for the social science* (6th edition). New York: Routledge.
- Robinson, J. P., Shaver, P. R., & Wrightsman, L. S. (1991). Criteria for scale selection and evaluation. *Measures of personality and social psychological attitudes*, 1, 1-16.
- Romero-Díaz de la Guardia, J. J., García-Garnica, M., Chacón-Cuberos, R., & Expósito-López, J. (2022). *Psychometric validation of a teamwork skills scale in a vocational training context*. SAGE Open. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440221103256>
- Seuneke, P., Papić-Blagojević, N., & Belotserkovsky, A. (2021). International cooperative development of VOOCs for VET teacher professionalisation: Lessons learned. In M. Willemsse (ed.), *15th annual EAPRIL Conference for Practitioner Research on Improving Learning: Learning in the Age of Industry 4.0*. Leuven.
- Španović, S., & Đukić, M. (2006). Nastavnička percepcija timske nastave. In O. Gajić (Ed.), *Evropske dimenzije promena obrazovnog sistema u Srbiji, I deo* (pp. 289-311). Novi Sad: Filozofski fakultet Univerziteta u Novom Sadu.
- Vasiljević, D., Stepić, G., & Ilić, M. (2017). Elementary school teachers' attitudes to teamwork. *Nastava i vaspitanje*, 66(1), 99-114.

Biographical notes

Dr **Nataša Papić-Blagojević** is a professor of applied studies in quantitative analysis and deputy director for projects at Novi Sad School of Business, Serbia, since 2005. Her research experience is presented by writing over 60 scientific papers in applied statistics and researching VET and HE.

Dr **Stevan Tomašević** is a lecturer and coordinator for projects at the Novi Sad School of Business, Serbia. He gained teaching experience by performing lectures and exercises in accounting, auditing, business analysis, business statistics and applied statistics.

Dr **Željko Račić** is a professor of applied studies and head of an office for international cooperation at Novi Sad School of Business, Serbia. He has more than 13 years of experience teaching undergraduate and master's courses in finance, international and national banking, and risk management.

Dr **Mirko Savić** is a full professor, and coordinator of the project centre at the faculty of the economics university of Novi Sad. Prof. Savić is a former member of the Commission for Accreditation and Quality Assurance in Serbia, HERE team (Higher Education Reform Expert) in Serbia, and Statistical Council of Republic of Serbia, ENQA expert.